

6 Try at Home Ayurvedic Treatments for Thyroid Abnormalities

The experts of [Ayurvedic Treatments for Thyroid Abnormalities](#) say that, in Ayurveda, harmonizing the body's energy is the key to managing thyroid. A sedentary lifestyle is associated with a thyroid illness. Thyroid illness is a lifestyle problem, not a disease. There are two forms of this illness. The thyroid gland's hormone production slows down in hypothyroidism. As a consequence, the body's metabolism slows down as well. Hypothyroidism causes a person to gain weight. Hyperthyroidism, on the other hand, is a condition in which the thyroid gland produces too much thyroid hormones. When a person has hyperthyroidism, he or she will lose weight.

Thyroid and Ayurveda

According to Ayurveda, Thyroid is most associated with the rise of vata and kapha dosha in the body. Doshas are biological energy that controls the human body's physical and mental operations.

The vata dosha is associated with air. Earth and water are characteristics of the kapha dosha. Thyroid disease is caused by an imbalance of these doshas.

He went on to say that Ayurveda believes in balancing the body's energies and rectifying the thyroxin hormone's circulation in the body to manage thyroid. It gives thyroid sufferers some simple home treatments that they may use to keep their thyroid under control.

Ayurveda offers some simple suggestions for increasing thyroxin hormone circulation in the body. Read on!

Eat A Diet That Balances Vata.

The rise of the vata dosha in the body, according to Ayurveda, might cause thyroid imbalance. If you have a thyroid condition, you should avoid eating foods that will raise your thyroid hormone levels.

Consume high-fiber foods such as bananas, spinach, beans, and legumes. You should eat three to four meals every day and not miss lunch or supper.

Foods composed of besan (gram flour) and maida should be avoided (all-purpose flour). They may cause an imbalance of the thyroid stimulating hormone by increasing vata in the body (TSH).

Foods That Boost Kapha Should Be Avoided

Thyroid weight gain is one of the most typical symptoms. It is suggested that you follow a kapha pacifying diet to regulate your weight gain and thyroid. Fresh veggies and fruits should always be consumed. Grain, bean, and nut meals are all good choices. At least one fruit each day should be consumed.

Kapha vardhak aahaar vihaar is not recommended in Ayurvedic medicine. This implies you should avoid kapha-inducing foods and lifestyles.

Milk and dairy products should be consumed in moderation.

Include Pranayama into Your Lifestyle

Pranayama is a Yoga technique for breathing regulation. Pranayama is recommended for thyroid patients because it helps to regulate the vata in the body, which helps to manage thyroid problems.

Thyroid sufferers will benefit greatly from pranayama. It has the ability to modulate thyroid and brain processes.

Pranayama methods such as kapal bharti and anulom-vilom should be practised.

Walking in the Morning

Sedentary behaviour might cause a thyroid stimulating hormone imbalance. As a result, daily morning walks are an Ayurvedic therapy for thyroid regulation.

Walking first thing in the morning may help you manage your thyroid by increasing the circulation of oxygenated blood in your body.

Every morning, go for a little stroll.

Massage

This is the simplest thyroid-fighting approach since you just have to relax. Not only will this assist to calm the vata, but it will also aid in the reduction of excess body fat caused by thyroid problems.

Abhyanga, or lubricating your body with oil, according to Ayurveda, might be a highly effective treatment for thyroid problems.

You will benefit much from abhyanga. It improves blood circulation and supplies nutrients to muscles and neurons. Thyroid sufferers benefit from it.

Try the Following Home Remedies

Treatment using natural therapies is typical of Ayurvedic traditions. The majority of these natural cures may be found in your kitchen. Grab some triphala, methi, ginger, or aloe vera if you're attempting to keep your thyroid levels in check. People are unaware that these compounds may be quite beneficial to thyroid sufferers.

Consume aloe vera leaf juice or raw aloe vera. It is quite effective in calming and balancing the vata and kapha energies in the body.

If you're a thyroid patient, it's a good idea to switch from caffeine-based drinks like tea and coffee to herbal tea.

Soak some coriander and cumin seeds overnight in water. Drink the water on an empty stomach first thing in the morning.